

Job Stress And Turnover Intentions Among School Teachers Of Punjab Pakistan

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: February 29, 2022</p> <p>Accepted: September 30, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Job Stress, Turnover Intentions, Descriptive Statistics, Inferential Statistics</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7178618</p>	<p><i>Job Stress is considered as a stimulator of turnover intentions among the employees of any organization. As the teachers belong to a noble profession i.e. profession of the Prophets, hence the researcher, in order to verify this supposition, conducted this descriptive, co-relational and cross-sectional study for determining the relationship between job stress and turnover intentions among different categories of teachers working in public sector schools of Punjab Pakistan. Due to shortage of time and financial resources, this study was delimited to Faisalabad Division. The sample of this study comprised 700 respondents selected by multi-stage proportionate stratified random sampling technique. Standardized scales were employed for determining the workplace stress and turnover intentions after taking permissions. In addition to descriptive statistics, inferential statistics i.e. Independent Sample t-test, One Way ANOVA, Pearson Correlations Co-efficient and Linear Regression were also calculated from the collected data using SPSS 23 with the aim to test the already formulated null hypotheses of the study. Based on the study findings, it was concluded that there is moderate level positive correlation between teachers' job stress and their turnover intentions as well as job stress is a significant predictor of teachers' turnover intentions.</i></p>

Introduction

Job Stress is the pressure and the tension which the employees have to face during the course of their duties due to unnatural demands. Job stress for current study refers to the score obtained by the participants on Workplace Stress Scale. A higher score represents a higher level of job stress.

As a whole, occupational stress has become a permanent feature of our day to day life. Stress is a complex term which has been defined by the researchers in different ways. Some of the researchers link it to an effect thinking it as a cause (Ganster&Schaubroeck, 1991; Jex, Beehr& Roberts, 1992; Karasek, 1979). In this regard, many researchers while defining job stress focused on the demand control or work strain model of Karasek (1979) like (Ganster&Schaubroeck, 1991; Liu, Spector &Jex, 2005; Totterdell, Wood & Wall, 2006; Fox & Spector, 2006). Three basic features of occupational stress have been explained by this model containing job demands, liberty of decision making at job (job decision latitude) and mental anxiety (psychological strain). A survey for exploring the way how different researchers considered occupational stress was conducted by renowned researchers as reported by Husain, Gulzar&Aqeel (2016) and found out the following three practical ways: as stimulus, reaction or response and as stimulus reaction (response) process. They further stated that a number of investigators considered it more appropriate to view occupational stress as stimulus reaction or response process. Ellis (2006) viewed occupational stress to be a response that exerts negative impact on the well-being of a person. As per view point of Janssen (2004), occupational stress is a response like burnout or anxiety.

Factors of job stress i.e. stressors can differ keeping in view the tasks assigned to the employees and the employer firm. Ormond, Keown-Gerrard & Kline (2003) through a research study found out that the common stressors of job included excessive load of work, wastage of precious time in meetings, shortage of liaison on the part of boss, useless messaging, nonexistence of criticism, absence of encouragement, complex roles, insufficient training, conflict in workers and deficiency of determination. Riaz&Ramzan (2013) viewed time management to be one of the major reasons of occupational stress. It has been pointed out by the research studies that the intensity of job stress in teaching is greater than the job stress in other professions (Darmody& Smith, 2016). According to Sing &Katoch (2017), usually job stress arises due to the imbalance between supposed labour and supposed remuneration, or it may also generate because of a feeling of having less control but great responsibilities in a profession. It was also indicated by them that lack of support from the co-workers in job and lack of job security may also enhance job stress among teachers. As per findings of Kokkinos (2007), the teachers' job stress is influenced by the following factors i.e. time constraints, issues pertaining to discipline, dearth of means, lack of acknowledgement and assistance at workplace and variety of the assignments supposed to perform. Job stress occurs due to the allotment of unanticipated assignments and uneven load of work which

are beyond abilities, expertise and awareness of the teachers (Xu et al., 2017). Stress is such a common phenomenon that almost none can deny to experience it. Stress can be traced in the lives of the employees working in varied jobs like teaching etc. Various kinds of changes in the organizations exert unwanted effects on the employees, upset them and cause job stress. These organizational changes may include forceful transfers, illegal or out of turn promotions, amendments in rules and regulations, disciplinary actions or punishments, non-competitive salary packages and the changes in the attitudes of society (Hamid, et. Al., 2015). Stress is considered as force having an unwanted effect on the productivity as well as efficacy of any firm cum its workers and might develop bodily and psychological ailments (Alavi, 1993). Corporal overtiredness and the strain which penetrate into the stature of mankind may be traced and cured with ease whereas, a stress which penetrates into the soul of the mankind is invisible and cannot be measured in a simple way. That is why, it exerts a damaging impact on the employees. Severe stress is not but a sheer wastage of human resource due to which the overall aim of the firm is at stake. Job stress affects employees' bodily along with their intellectual state, it also exerts great effect on the level of their satisfaction, output and absenteeism (Tennant, 2001). Stress is the disproportion of supposed needs and means available to an employee (Saeed & Farooqi, 2014). Stress generates when a worker is uncertain about his competence to encounter the fears to their well-being and their skill to meet the requirements perfectly supposed be met by that employee (Lazarus, 1966). Workplace/Job Stress may also be defined as a damaging bodily and psychological reaction occurred due to the clash between the demands of job and the extent of control which the employee uses to attain these demands (Arandelović&Ilić, 2006). Blaug, Kenyon & Lekhi, (2007) found strong relationship of job stress, sorrow and sickness among people. According to Detert, Caravella, Derosia&Duquette, (2006), the following factors develop job stress among teachers i.e. excessive load of work, unpleasant terms with co-workers, role conflict, disciplinary issues, pressure due to shortage of time, role ambiguity, unscrupulous working environment, self-esteem, less cooperation on the part of friends, family members and unmotivated fellows in the students. Avey, Luthans& Jenson (2009) conducted a research in which they concluded that occupational stress, these days, has taken the form of a common issue for the managers dealing in human resource. Job Stress is considered as the physical and psychological condition which an employee has to face when he finds his resources inadequate to meet with the pressures and requirements of that very situation through which he is passing (Michie, 2002). Ullrich& Fitzgerald (1990) are of the view that Job Stress is the outcome of loss of balance between the needs of the employer and the worker's capacity to meet with those requirements. Job Stress may also be explained as the undesirable psychological condition arising out due to the interaction which takes place in employee and his employer or the employee and the environment of his work place. According to a fundamental assumption of stress theory the psychosomatic stressors including role stress and absence of control along with no or less social support exert damaging effects on the employees' health as well as the productivity of the organization (Karasek& Theorell, 1990). Job Stress has been defined by Jamal (2005) as a person's response to the features of the settings of his work place which look frightening from emotional cum physical point of view. Most of the times it has been observed that the employees who have to face extraordinary job stress don't enjoy good health, are unable to show good performance, have less motivation level and feel insecure at work settings. It is also worth mentioning here that their organizations remain unable to earn a good name as compared to those organizations whose employees don't have to face job stress. Undue job stress generates physical as well as psychological ailments and maladies in the person, which will result in his decreased performance (Işıkhan, 2004). Job stress is the reaction of the employee to the unnecessary pressure he faces in work life (Genc, 2005). Ali, Ishtiaq& Ahmad (2013) conducted a study to determine the effects of occupational stress on job performance of Pakistani teachers. The major findings of the study revealed that job stress affects physical as well as mental health and it also results in poor quality of production along with less output. Prasad, Vaidya & Kumar (2016) through a multinomial regression approach research investigated teacher's performance as a function of occupational stress and coping with reference to CBSE affiliated school teachers in and around Hyderabad. The results of this study verify the existence of medium level workplace stress among school teachers which should be removed in order to enhance their performance. Hanif, Tariq & Nadeem (2011) also conducted a research on the public and private school teachers working in primary and secondary schools of Islamabad Pakistan in order to explore the role of personal and job related variables in teacher stress and job performance. In addition to it, this study was also supposed to know the relationship of levels and sources of job stress with the performance of school teachers. It was found out that teachers' stress and job performance were negatively correlated with each other.

Turnover Intention is the plan of willful departure of a worker from the organization he is serving in or working with. Turnover Intention for current study refers to the score obtained by the participants on Turnover Intention Scale. A higher score represents a higher level of Turnover Intentions.

Imran et al., (2017) defined turnover intention as a plan considered by a worker to quit his workplace or a conscious struggle on the part of the employee in search of an employment out of the firm he is working with. Teaching has been considered as being a Turning Gate by some researchers (e.g. Ingersoll, 2003; Hanushek, Kain& Rivkin, 2003) which stresses the rate of turnover in teacher community. An employee's design and

thought to leave the existing employment at a particular time is termed as turnover intention (Fong & Mahfar, 2013). It is a plan to shift from a job or firm willingly (Schyns, Torka & Goessling, 2007). A trend to abandon any employer organization with one's own consent (Gaertner, 1999) or it may also be defined as an employee's longing to desert the business body with which the employee is working (Liu & Onwuegbuzie, 2012). According to the definition given by Tett & Meyer (1993), turnover intention is the deliberate search for a better job in any other firm. Another definition of turnover by the same authors says: It is the end of a person's service in a particular firm. Willful departure of a worker from any organization is known as turnover (Caroon et al., 2004) and the plans to turnover are turnover intentions. The ratio with which experienced workforce quits the organization and fresh workforce joins that organization is termed as turnover. The replacement of the employees working in an organization in a fixed time span is also known as turnover and the intents to actual turnover is known as turnover intentions.

Voluntary turnover and involuntary turnover are considered to be two major categories of turnover. If an employee resigns from any organization willingly then this turnover will be voluntary whereas if an employee has to say goodbye to his organization because his services are no more required by that organization then this kind of turnover will be called as involuntary turnover (Price & Mueller, 1981). It can be found out by going through the pages of history that the turnover which is involuntary usually supports the interest of the organization whereas voluntary turnover exerts damaging effects on the prorganization (McShane & Williams, 1993). The possibility of the staff members exiting from the organization can be judged by knowing the extent of turnover intentions. Hence it provides assistance in minimizing turnover as a whole.

Above average turnover intentions were observed by Cerit (2015) in teachers. Teachers' turnover intention has been reflected in literature as a major problem which many countries are facing now a days (Liu & Onwuegbuzie, 2012). The turnover intentions require new recruitment on urgent basis, deprive the organization from the expert employees, generate depression and demotivate the remaining employees and minimize organizational output (Cakir, 2001). The impact of teachers' turnover intentions on the quality of teaching, curriculum and students' achievements is also negative (Loeb & Darling-Hammond, 2005). For numerous years, intention to leave remained a grave matter for administration but presently it has taken the form of the most important issue for the business bodies (Chen, Lin & Lien, 2011).

Akhtar et al. (2016) conducted a survey study for determining the impact of job satisfaction and remuneration on turnover intentions on private schools of Okara, Pakistan. The findings of the study found turnover intentions have significantly negative correlation with job satisfaction and remuneration. The employee's turnover intention may be eradicated by making some perfections in the employee's circumstances (Ercan, 2016).

To examine the relationship **Job Stress, Turnover Intentions**, psychological well-being and grit among 325 English as Foreign Language (EFL) teachers of Iran, Nazari & Ogghyanous (2021) conducted a study, keeping in view their teaching experience and found strong correlation between their occupational stress / turnover intentions and grit / psychological well-being. Mosadeghard, Ferlie & Rosenberg (2011) conducted a research to assess the association between job stress, quality of working life and turnover intentions among hospital employees. The findings of the study showed that a positive connection was found between job stress and turnover intentions of the workers of Iranian hospitals. Arshadi & Damiri (2013) also conducted a research on the work force of National Drilling Company of Iran in order to determine the relationship of job stress with turnover intention and job performance: moderating role of organizational based self-esteem and concluded that job stress and turnover intentions were positively related. It means if the level of job stress is high, then turnover intentions will also be severe and vice versa. Job stress exerts a bad influence on the job satisfaction level of the workers and resultantly their productivity decreases and intentions to quit the organization are multiplied (Applebaum, Fowler, Fiedler, Osinubi and Robson, 2010). A great number of researchers concluded through their studies that turnover intentions intensify by increasing job stress (Chen et al., 2011; Applebaum et al., 2010). Noor & Maad (2008) concluded that work stress and turnover intentions are positively correlated. Ertürk (2022) conducted a quantitative research to determine the relationship of teachers' quality of work life on job satisfaction and turnover intentions among teachers working in primary schools of central district of Bolu, Turkey. The finding of this study revealed highly positive relationship between dimensions of stress in work life and turnover intentions. This study recommended to increase job satisfaction in order lessen turnover intentions. Lack of job security or job satisfaction rises the turnover among the employees and reduces organizational commitment in them (Fatimah, Noraishah, Nasir & Khairiddin, 2012). Like Liu & Onwuegbuzie, (2012) and Yin & Yang, (2002), Xu et al., (2017) also confirmed the availability of positive relationship between job stress and turnover intentions among teachers.

Keeping in view the literature review cited above it can be summed up that with the advancement of Science and Technology, the pace of life has multiplied. The demands and the requirements of every organization are touching the sky. They set high targets for their employees which are not easy to achieve. These high and illogical targets on the part of the business bodies may create job stress resulting in the production of turnover intentions among the workers of the firm. Through the search of the pages of history it can be easily traced that the role of teacher was uni-dimensional and very simple in past as the teacher of that

time was confined only to teaching. But in present age the role of a teacher has become very complex and multi-dimensional. The teacher of today is not restricted to teaching only but he is supposed to perform various other tasks including increasing enrollment, decreasing dropout, ensuring 95% attendance of the enrolled students on daily basis, achieving cleanliness targets of the school, ensuring functionality of the available facilities, holding parent teacher meetings, involving school council for utilization of funds like Farooq-e-Taleem Fund and Non Salary Budget, performing duty for the smooth conduct of PEC and Board examinations as invigilation or supervisory staff, doing election duty, extending services for census being a national cause, participating in polio eradication campaign and at the same time showing better results as compared to the results of PEC and concerned Educational Board. Moreover, he has become more accountable before the government and public also. The government is pressing the teachers very hard for doing more and more without taking into consideration the ground realities which is causing lot of job stress among school teachers (Farooq & Kai, 2017). Demir (2016) is of the view that the quality of work of the teachers weakens if the conditions of their workplace are not favourable and workload is not justified. When he tries to achieve all these targets of his job fixed by his employer i.e. SED and he feels him unable to attain them, ultimately he faces job stress which affects the quality of his life by producing numerous mental health disorders. Consequently, the organizations fail to compete with their counterparts in the same field. So, the organizations condemn such employees and enhance pressure on them which may result in production as well as development of turnover intentions in them. As it is crystal clear that SED is an organization and school teachers of different categories are its employees who are facing job stress. Hence the present study is being designed to fill in this gap by knowing the two way relationship of job stress and turnover intentions among school teachers belonging to SED Punjab.

There is no doubt that most of the research studies found out positive relationship between job stress and turnover intentions (Mosadeghard, Ferlie & Rosenberg, 2011; Arshadi & Damiri, 2013) but as teaching is a noble profession and the profession of the Prophets so it seems quite appropriate, logical and essential to conduct this study to know whether the job stress has same positive relationship with turnover intentions in different categories of teachers i.e. PSTs, ESTs, and SSTs or it is otherwise working in SED Punjab? The two variables are interconnected and influence teachers' performance to a great extent; therefore, it is necessary to find out their relationship as discussed earlier. On the other hand this study is also of great value as it will find out the relationship of job stress with turnover intentions of teachers considering their demographic characteristics i.e. gender and qualification of the teachers. It has been observed that though some researches have been conducted on the job stress and turnover intentions of the teachers but no research study deals with the same population as this study does. Therefore, the researcher planned to conduct this study.

The findings of this study will enable the concerned authorities to take appropriate action to address this issue of vital significance. It will prove a reference for future researches and activate a plethora of research in this comparatively less explored area. Moreover, the current study will prove a valuable addition in the existing body of knowledge regarding issues of school education. This research study will also be significant for the researchers, teachers, educationists, planners, managers, administrators and other stakeholders of the concerned area along with SED Punjab.

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant relationship between Job Stress and Turnover Intentions of school teachers.
2. Job stress is not a significant predictor of Turnover Intentions of school teachers.
3. There is no significant effect of demographic characteristics (gender and qualification) of teachers on their Job Stress and Turnover Intentions.

Delimitation of the Study

Owing to shortage of time and financial resources, this study will be delimited to:

1. All public sector schools of four Districts of Faisalabad Division (i.e. Chiniot, Faisalabad, Jhang and Toba Tek Singh) of Punjab Province.
2. PSTs, ESTs and SSTs working in public sector schools of the above-mentioned districts only.

Methods

Research Design

This survey-based study is descriptive, co-relational and cross-sectional. Quantitative approach was employed in this study.

Population of the Study

All 47237 (male and female) teachers of different categories i.e. PSTs, ESTs and SSTs working in public sector schools of all four districts of Faisalabad Division constituted the population for this study (Report on Annual School Census, 2017-18).

Sample and Sampling Technique

A sample consisting of 700 respondents with equal representation of both male and female genders and considering urban and rural distribution of the public schools was selected by multi-stage proportionate

stratified random sampling technique from all four districts of Faisalabad Division. The following table shows the sample size and sampling technique.

Graph 1

Research Instruments

i) Workplace Stress Scale

To determine the job stress of teachers, the Workplace Stress Scale developed by the American Institute of Stress (1998) was employed. This scale is comprised of 10 items. The respondent is required to enter a number from 1 to 10 which describes him the best. The numbers 1 to 4 express strongly disagree, 5 to 7 show somewhat agree and 8 to 10 describe strongly agree. To get total job stress score, the replies to each question are added. The 10-30 scores indicate that the respondent handles the job stress well whereas the scores 40-60 reflect moderately well and scores 70-100 show that the respondent is facing problems which need to be fixed.

ii) Turnover Intention Scale

Whereas the Turnover Intention Scale developed by Roodt (2004) was employed for the measurement of turnover intentions. There is no doubt that this scale was designed to measure intentions to stay but it has been proved valid for measuring turnover intentions as well (Martin & Roodt, 2008). It is a 15-items questionnaire which employs an intensity response scale comprising of five points with extreme intensities at both opposite poles for scoring. It was not published (Martin, & Roodt, 2008). For further clarification, the example of the following item can be considered: "How often have you considered leaving your job?" ("Never" 1-Indicates rare possibility to "Always" 5-Shows very high possibility). For calculation of the total score, the individual item scores are added up. This scale was found reliable as having Cronbach's Alpha coefficient value of 0.913 (Jacob & Roodt, 2011). Faisal (2010) declared 0.70 or higher reliability score as acceptable.

Data Collection Procedures

The researcher sought institutional permission for data collection from respective heads of departments / institutes and collected the data through various modes.

Data Analysis Procedures

In addition to descriptive statistics, Pearson Correlation, Linear Regression Analysis and t-test were calculated in order to draw meaningful conclusions from the collected data using SPSS 23. Moreover ANOVA was used to measure cause and effect relationship between the variables. Implications of the results were duly discussed at the end of this research report.

RESULTS

All the collected data were placed into SPSS for analysis, initially the data collected were descriptively analyzed in the light of research objectives and then through inferential statistics the research hypotheses were tested.

Table 1

Relationship between Job Stress and turnover intentions among teachers

Pearson Correlation	Mean	SD	N	R	Sig
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Male	350	50.0	54.2629	11.425	0.5714	698	.065	.394
Female	350	50.0	54.2057	11.971				

Another important aspect of gender-wise perspective in this study was related to the comparison of gender and job stress feelings. The mean score of male and female respondents about their job stress was 54.2629 and 54.2057 with standard deviations from mean scores were 11.425 and 11.971 that reflects same opinions about job stress which was confirmed by the mean differences 0.5714, t value .065 and these are not significant as the sig value was .394 higher than .05.

Therefore, there is no significant difference between the perceptions of male and female about their job stress at workplace and gender has no significant effect on the job stress of teachers. Further, the null hypothesis that is there is no significant difference between male and female and gender has no significant effects on the job stress of teachers was accepted.

Table No 5

Teachers' differences on the basis of their academic qualification regarding Turnover Intentions

Qualification	Descriptive results		ANOVA Results				
	Mean scores	Standard Deviation	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Matric	39.2632	8.37219	911.121	4	227.780	3.074	.016
Intermediate	40.4286	8.58820	51496.163	695	74.095		
Graduation	39.0526	8.04690	52407.284	699			
Masters	39.2719	8.88795					
MPhil/PhD	42.2500	7.99080					

This table explains teachers' academic qualifications and their turnover intentions. The highest mean scores were found for MPhil/PhD, and Intermediate 42.25 and 40.4286 respectively, these differences among teachers from the perspectives of their academic qualifications were significant, because MPhil/ PhD qualified teachers were found more inclined toward turnover intentions, as shown by the f value 3.074 which is significant at .016 which is less than .05. Furthermore, high qualified teachers always strived for higher grades and new portfolios which are matching to their qualifications.

Therefore, the results illustrate the higher qualification leads towards turnover intentions among teachers at school level, which enables the researcher to reject the null hypothesis as higher qualification holders' experiences more turnover intentions as compared to lower academic qualification.

Table 6

Teachers' differences on the basis of their academic qualification regarding Job Stress

Qualification	Descriptive results		ANOVA Results				
	Mean scores	Standard Deviation	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Matric	57.0526	10.67954	886.118	4	221.530	1.626	.166
Intermediate	57.0476	14.36829	94689.459	695	136.244		
Graduation	54.3474	10.45331	95575.577	699			
Masters	53.5079	11.73576					
MPhil/PhD	55.9000	11.98206					

This table explains teachers' academic qualifications and their job stress at workplace. The highest mean scores were found for matric and intermediate qualified teachers 57.0526 and 57.0476 respectively, however the differences among these academic qualifications were not significant as these academic qualifications don't lead towards the any differences on their job stress at workplace because the f value 1.626 is not significant at .166.

Therefore, it was concluded that teachers' academic qualifications have nothing with the perceptions of teachers' job stress at their workplace which enables the researcher to accept the null hypothesis because qualification has no significant effect or differences from the perspectives of job stress.

Study Findings

The major study findings are presented as followed;

1. The correlation co-efficient r value .558 significant at .000 illustrated a moderate positive correlation between teachers' turnover intentions and their job stress at workplace (Table 1).
2. The results of linear regression, f value 316.142 and r^2 value .312 showed that job stress is a significant predictor of teachers' turnover intentions and explain it up to 31%. (Table 2).
3. There were no gender-wise differences between male and female teachers on the study variables (Job Stress and Turnover intentions) as showed by the t value -.053, 1.621 and .065 which was not significant at .958, 105 and .394. (Table 3 and 4).
4. No significant differences were observed in teachers' job stress on the basis of their academic qualification whereas significant differences were found among teachers regarding turnover intentions on the basis of their qualification because MPhil/PhD qualified teachers were found more inclined toward turnover intentions, as shown by the f value 3.074 which is significant at .016 which is less than .05 (Table 5 and 6).

Discussions

Job stress was one of the main study variables and the results extracted from the analysis revealed that teachers have low level of job stress at their workplace. This stress was because of working environment prevailing in schools, low authority, time constraints and absence of good work recognitions. The same results were found in the study of Ali, Ishtiaq & Ahmad (2013) who concluded that teachers in Pakistan are facing job stress and it had negative impact on their overall professional performances, the same were also supported by the findings of the Prasad, Vaidya & Kumar (2016) who conducted this research work in Hyderabad on CBSE school teachers who were recorded a medium level of job stress among teachers.

The results also revealed that majority of teachers have turnover intentions, the frequently thinking and striving for another job, and were not satisfied with the fulfilment of teachers' professional needs. These results matched with the study results of Ekabu, Kalai & Nyagah (2018) which confirmed that workload and the competitive environment at school across the world are strong indicators of teachers' turnover intentions. The same results were established by Yang et al. (2009); Kim (2015) and Liu et al. (2013) who concluded that teachers in China have high rate of turnover intentions due to the introduction of new system of education, lower educational resources and high expectations from the community and other stakeholders.

Furthermore, this job stress was found responsible for the turnover intentions of teachers in this study. Teachers belong to primary school in particular and to elementary and higher secondary schools in general were found more inclined towards turnover intentions. Avey, Luthans and Jenson (2009) viewed that teachers working time, workload, physical and psychological aspect of their school atmosphere are some of the prominent indicators responsible for their turnover intentions. There are other factors too that includes striving for higher grades, more better jobs, professional identity and home related factors but work stress is considered a bulging one.

The results also indicated that majority of the teachers face low level job stress therefore, it hasn't affected their physical, mental and psychological health. However, according to Michie (2002) teachers facing high or moderate level job stress are always exposed to sever physical and psychological health issues and they are required to take medicines regularly. Hanif, Tariq & Nadeem (2011) in addition to other results in their study conducted in Islamabad concluded that teacher experience low level of job stress which are same results yield by this study.

Furthermore, the correlation between job stress and turnover intentions among teachers was found significant, the nature of the strength of this correlation was moderate which was confirmed by the results of Hanif, Tariq & Nadeem (2011) and Prasad, Vaidya & Kumar (2016) which illustrated that job stress is the strong predictable construct of employees' turnover intentions. Teachers who are experiencing job stress at workplace have more inclination to switch to other professions, organizations and employment firms with the intentions of relief and satisfaction. Furthermore, as compared to the current study and cited studies, teachers in China face high level work stress due to the change in their system of education and limited resources as concluded by Yang et al. (2009).

Additionally, gender was not found a significant indicator for job stress and turnover intentions in this study. However, these results were different from the results of Yang et al. (2009) who concluded that male teachers experience less job stress at workplace as compared to female gender. These differences may be due to general cultural differences in Pakistan and China.

From the perspectives of designations PST teachers were found more inclined towards turnover intentions as compared to elementary and secondary school teachers. In relation to this, the study of Kim (2015) concluded that teachers' intrinsic motivation is a significant mediating factor that reduce or trigger the turnover intentions among employees. Therefore, these results were confirmed by the mentioned study.

In nutshell most of the results of study were found in congruence with the results of already published studies. It also endorsed that job stress at workplace and turnover intentions is a significant problem faced especially by teachers likewise other professionals in their respective fields and affect their performance, physical and mental well-being and overall quality of life negatively.

Conclusions

Keeping in view the research findings following research conclusions were drawn;

Teachers have low level stress at their workplace, they are mostly affected by their low authority against high responsibilities, lack of appreciation for their performances and lower control on the working life reflected that they have stress. However, this level of teachers' stress was low and it was believed that teachers have capabilities to deal with this stress.

The findings revealed that most of the teachers have the feelings of to quit the job i.e. turnover intentions. These feelings of turnover are because of multiple factors such as unfulfillment of personal needs, frustration on the non-achievement of professional targets, attraction / opportunities for new jobs with better salary packages and job nature. Furthermore, it was concluded that teachers have moderate level turnover intentions.

Furthermore, it was proved that teachers concluded that teachers' job stress and turnover intentions are positively correlated with each other, the increase in the one variable resultantly increases the occurrences of the second variable. Those schools where teachers face job stress due to school atmosphere, collegial problems, leadership undue pressures or other related factors are more inclined towards turnover intentions. It was also concluded that turnover intentions are highly significant among primary school teachers as compared to elementary and secondary teachers.

Furthermore, it was also concluded that teachers' qualification, were among the strong predictors of teachers' turnover intentions at school level. Additionally, high qualified teachers, were found more willing to turnover intentions as compared to low qualified.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions of the study the following recommendations were made to the concerned stakeholders;

1. The conclusions showed that teachers have low level job stress at workplace. Therefore, it was recommended to the school heads of the sample group that they may arrange capacity building sessions with teachers to identify the background reasons responsible to the stress of teachers. These school leaders were also recommended to work on the collegiality among teachers at school.
2. Moderate level turnover intentions were identified among majority of the teachers, therefore, it was recommended to the authorities of education department to provide in-service trainings, work for the well-being, and provide consultative and motivational sessions to the teachers in collaboration with Department of Education and Psychological studies of public sector universities.
3. It was also recommended that the monitoring policies, suspension of casual leaves and other such policies that lead to teachers' turnover intentions may be re-considered, because these turnover intentions will never let the teachers to deliver their best which will negatively contribute towards students' development and achievement.
4. For future researchers it was recommended that they investigate the same problem at university level and in public and private sector institutions.
5. Furthermore, it would further be more productive to explore the turnover intentions as a phenomenon so that it could be explored qualitatively.

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